

IMAGE OF THE MOTHER IN THE WORK OF O' TKIR HASHIMOV

To'rayeva Aziza Ilkhombojeva¹

Matsafayeva Nasiba Kodamovna²

¹⁻²Urganch city, Khorezm region, general secondary school No. 1

Teachers of mother tongue and literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529061>

Abstract: This article focuses on the work of O'tkir Hashimov, one of the leading representatives of Uzbek literature. In addition, comments were made about the influence of the period covered in the work on the inner psyche and experiences of the image of Mothers in the works of this artist.

Key words: work of art, external action, inner experience, hero's priesthood, artistic image, Mother's image, tragedy, period of crisis.

The role of fiction is incomparable in the formation of our national consciousness, consciousness and worldview, which is based on our national values formed over the centuries, today is imbued with the ideology of independence, and at the same time, it leads us to the great universal spirituality. When it comes to works of art, there are opinions among literary people: "*A work of art is a reduced existence or a model of reality*", which first of all confirms that every created work of art is a reflection of human life. When it comes to O'tkir Hashimov, who contributed to the development of literature by describing the recent past and present life of our nation, all its complexities, national traditions and values with consistent artistic expressions in his artistic works, the literary critic U. Normatov wrote the following can be cited: "*... in the years of independence, many writers who created during the Soviet era were forced to re-edit their previously created works from the perspective of the ideology of independence. But O'tkir Hashimov's works did not need such revisions*".¹

Of course, these words were not spoken in vain. Because in the works of O'tkir Hashimov, the external actions and inner experiences of people's lives serve as leadership. In his works, O'tkir Hashimov describes the boundaries of the spiritual world of man and time through the priesthood of his heroes. Academician B. Nazarov commented on the writer's creativity: "*I would like to liken Otkir Hashimov's work to a river that overflows and flows with intensity and grace... Otkir Hashimov's works are like a river I didn't pretend. If you read, you will clearly see, understand and feel the adjectives in their language.*"

Obviously, artistic images do not enter any work by themselves. When a writer chooses a hero for his work, he first of all looks for him in his surroundings.

¹ Normatov U. Umidbaxsh tamoyillar. -T.: Ma'naviyat, 2000.

That's why Chingiz Aitmatov says: "A work of art is a story of a person about a person." When the creator chooses a hero for the work, first of all, he focuses on the influence of the heroes of the work on the society, social environment, and vice versa, on the life of the heroes. For example, in O'tkir Hashimov's story "The Last Victim of the War", we can see the effects of the Second World War on people's lifestyle, as well as on their priesthood. The main character of the story is Aunt Umri. Mother, that is, Aunt Umri, is forced to steal from the yard of her second son Shaikrom for Shone'mat. Through this theft, the writer reveals the complexity of the era, its influence on the fate of the heroes and its tragic consequences.

This tragedy happened as a result of the action of the boy Shoikrom, who was trying to catch the thief. The result ends with the tragic death of Mushfiq's mother. So, was there malice in the mother's heart, or ignorance, evil in her heart? After all, he had to do this for his child! Who is the thief? A thief is an age and a society based on ignorance and evil. For this reason, the writer considers the thefts and murders of Umri Kholo and Shoikrom, first of all, based on the life of the time. At the root of these considerations is the war and its consequences. The impact of the war on the mother's priesthood is also expressed in the novel "Between Two Doors" by O'tkir Hashimov. The images of Kara amma, Rabiya, and Rana in the novel are a clear example of this. We can see the influence of the era in the fate of these mothers in the description of the events that happened in their lives.

In the episodes of Kara Amma's waiting for her son Kimsan, Rabia's becoming the mother of a boy named Muzaffar, Rana's inability to get rid of her conscience, giving up her child, the characters show that the moral qualities and maturity of MOTHERS, their spiritual bottom and poverty is a crisis of the times. , describes in outward actions and inner feelings. In short, O'tkir Hashimov, while painting the image of the era and the Mother, sets the main goal of artistic analysis of the basis of people's life, spiritual and moral beliefs in each of his works.

References:

1. Normatov U. Hopeful principles.-T.: Ma'naviyat, 2000.
2. Nazarov B. The writer who won the people's love.-T.: Classic word. 2011.
3. Yoldosh Q., Yoldosh M. Fundamentals of artistic analysis.-T.: Kamalak. 2016;
4. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
5. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 353-362.